

Flexible Electronics for Commercial and Defense Applications

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Introduction: To date, there has been a strong consensus that U.S. flexible electronics technology and manufacturing efforts have demonstrated the potential for significant US-based job creation in small businesses to Fortune-500 companies. These jobs will impact across product supply chains, from raw materials production to retail sales of new devices. Flexible electronics is enabling a technology base that has the opportunity for the next high-tech manufacturing job creation. Early silicon CMOS manufacturing created high paying manufacturing jobs in US fabrication lines. Today, many of these jobs are moving to foreign Countries. Flexible electronics manufacturing approaches open the opportunity for innovative, low-cost fabrication techniques combining traditional US-strengths in plate-to-plate semiconductor manufacturing with roll-to-roll printing. Such approaches will enable mid-size companies to enter into manufacturing thereby broadening the job creation within the US. These innovative approaches to achieve the low-cost and high volume products will enable a US manufacturing dominance in an emerging Global industry. Future flexible electronics commercial and Defense Department applications include; wearable and medical sensors, structural monitoring devices, medical sensors, soft robotics, Internet of Things, and integrated array antennas on structures.

Flexible Electronics Review:

Flexible electronics technology encompasses a wide range of technologies. Perhaps the earliest example of flexible electronics was the Xerox organic photoreceptors for analog xerography (1). Most recently, The US Army's Flexible Display program demonstrated, in 2012, the World's largest flexible organic light emitting diode display (2). By 2015, flexible display technologies have been integrated into commercial portable electronic applications from smart-phones to smart watches. Flexible display technology depends on the manufacturing of a three-metal layer thin film transistor array on flexible substrates. Thin film transistors (TFT) have unique electronic properties suited for display applications. Fig. 1 shows a TFT and typical current-voltage characteristic with mobilities from 1 to 20 $\text{cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{cm}$ depending on the active channel material. TFTs have an operating stability adequate for low-duty cycle display applications.

In 2012, the US Army's Flexible Display program with the Defense Threat Reduction Agency extended the flexible

display thin film transistor manufacturing processes to flexible digital x-ray imaging arrays. Digital x-ray technology has very similar electronic characteristic requirements as displays, transistor mobilities of $1\text{-}10\text{cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$ and the demonstrated operating stability is adequate for the low-duty cycle x-ray imaging applications. A critical electrical property for display and digital x-ray imagers is the off-current of the transistors. TFTs have demonstrated off-currents in the low femto-amperes. Fig 2 illustrates the cross section of digital x-ray pixel. The basic operation starts with x-ray photons incident on a scintillator with a scale that corresponds to the x-ray absorption characteristics of the material. The scintillator linearly converts the total x-ray photon flux to a visible photon flux. The visible photon flux is then linearly measured with an amorphous silicon p-i-n photodiode where the accumulated charge from the photodiode corresponds to the incident x-ray photon flux. The accumulated charge from the photon diode is read out of the pixel through a thin film transistor. A flexible digital x-ray array requires manufacturing of the amorphous silicon photodiode and the thin film transistor array on a flexible substrate. The current approaches leverage traditional glass-based manufacturing approaches used for displays and digital x-ray commercial products. Fig. 2 includes an image of a flexible x-ray panel manufacturing at the Arizona State University Flexible Display and Electronic Center along with Xerox PARC for the package integration (3).

Similar flexible array sensors have been speculated to include electric-field imaging, acoustic imaging and neutron detectors (4). The realization of these future large-area array flexible sensor applications will rely on adapting traditional photolithography based manufacturing on flexible substrates. Electronic devices with displays and digital x-ray imagers require both large-area transistor arrays and high performance electronics for computation, memory, and communications. However, the operating stability of thin film transistors has been shown to be too low for traditional digital and analog electronic applications (5, 6). Hence, the same thin film transistor technology cannot complete the device systems to realize fully-flexible devices for commercial and Defense Department application. A different approach must be developed to integrate sensors with the required high performance electronic devices and power components to achieve the vision of fully-flexible ultra-light weight compact devices.

Flexible Hybrid Electronics:

To realize the flexible electronics commercial opportunities, the electronics require the carrier mobility and operating stability of silicon complementary metal oxide semiconductors (Si CMOS). As well many of the commercial and Defense Department applications require integration of the electronic devices with sensors and power components. The Electronics Manufacturing Services is a large segment of the electronic industry that manufacture electronic packaging for consumer and Defense applications. Flexible hybrid electronics (FHE) is an innovative manufacturing industry segment at the intersection of the electronics industry and the high-precision printing industry creating the next-generation of sensor platforms that conform, stretch or have reduced weight. The critical components that must be advanced from the traditional EMS manufacturing industry are; Device Integration and Packaging, materials, Printed Flexible Components and Microfluidics, modeling and design, and Standards, Test & Reliability.

FHE Manufacturing Industry

“Flexible”: final technology demonstrators, and to the extent necessary the integrated components, are mechanically compliant, such that the systems can conform, bend, stretch, or fold.

“Hybrid”: disparate component electronic technologies not traditionally available for flexible systems (such as thinned dies processed from traditional foundries, foundry-based or processed passives, foundry-based or processed sensors, and power) are integrated through innovation of established processes (such as pick and place, printing, lithography) into single and multilayer flexible architectures.

“Electronics”: performance of the final technology platform demonstration derives from the integrated functionality of the various electronic components, including logic, communication, sensing, power, and memory.

Device Integration and Packaging; Device integration and packaging is a key manufacturing challenge towards realizing flexible hybrid electronics commercial and defense technologies. The manufacturing approaches will leverage foundry-based high performance electronics that may include additional thinning for flexibility as needed. For many applications, the highest performance Si CMOS electronics is not required and older Si CMOS manufacturing nodes can be leveraged for performance-cost balance. Likewise, the integration of foundry-based sensors such as MEMs and other necessary sensor devices into flexible packages is a component of the manufacturing challenges. The manufacturing strategy may include manufacturing processes for discrete electronics and sensors where the manufacturing cost-models specifically indicate a benefit, such as highly specialized sensors based on unique materials.

The integration of foundry-based components with printed components will require unique printing approaches with reliable, high-speed registration techniques for multi-layer

devices. In addition, pick-and-place tools must be compatible with both thinned devices and flexible, non-traditional substrates, which could include plastic structures (e.g., elastomers), textiles, and breathable cloths. For some applications, tens or hundreds of simultaneous assemblies may be required in large panel formats. In many cases, these fabrication/integration steps must be accomplished at low temperatures compatible with the flexible substrates. Automated and robotic approaches are expected to play a central role in enabling device package and integration.

Materials; Includes conductive and active inks and pastes, and novel substrates that flex and stretch, and of low-cost renewable sources such as textiles and cellulose. A critical materials manufacture challenge is scale-up of manufacturing processes for the range of materials required in robust and fully packaged systems. Printed components (e.g., sensors, interconnects, passives) require high quality metal and dielectric inks that provide both flexibility and performance. In many cases, inks compatible with benign solvents and with low-temperature sinter/cure processes are needed to prevent damage to the substrate and other device components. Materials scale-up may include non-inks printed for interconnects, ball-grid arrays, such as low temperature solders, and other molten metal approaches. Batch-to-batch reproducibility of ink characteristics has been widely reported to be lacking and is essential for enabling printed components in FHE products. FHE devices also require flexible substrates with adequate temperature, chemical, mechanical, and environmental stability for varied applications. Substrates are also needed that are compatible with through-layer vias (for high density interconnects in multi-layer circuit designs) and low-temperature planarization processes. Finally, packaged FHE devices will also require both encapsulant and adhesive materials that are compatible (coefficient of thermal expansion, chemical, etc.) with FHE components and that will survive typical stresses and strains of FHE products.

Printed Flexible Components and Microfluidics; The manufacturing challenges in printed and flexible components for sensors and other discrete device components must address compatibility with the other process and cost balance with assembly of sensors.

Modeling & Design; Modeling and design encompasses standards and practices essential to minimizing barriers in supplier/customer relationships. New materials sets, manufacturing processes, and applications present a number of challenges ranging from durability to interface standards to design rules. In the case of durability, mechanical and environmental requirements must be defined for a range of use types. To enable plug-and-play assembly of hybrid devices with mixed signals and with components from multiple suppliers, interface/interconnect standards must be established. Similarly, to minimize both part count as well as power consumption, layout/design rules must be determined.

Standards, Test & Reliability; As standards are developed and validated, testing and metrology techniques must be identified and/or matured in order to confirm that standards are being met. Throughout the manufacturing life-cycle, in-

situ metrology is essential for minimizing defects. In-line, high-speed, and automated quality control tools are needed to monitor performance (e.g., conductivity) as well geometry/registration of the multi-component devices. Equally important is the development and/or validation of testing strategies/techniques to ensure adequate quality and reliability in commercial and military environments. Durability testing should evaluate, for example, the mechanical, thermal, and chemical response of FHE products. Although standards, testing, and metrology are well-established for traditional PCBs, FHE manufacturers have only begun to consider standards for new materials sets and manufacturing processes as well as the metrology needed to test FHE devices.

Conclusion: To realize the manufacturing challenges, the Defense Department established a Manufacturing Institute in Flexible Hybrid Electronics (7). The manufacturing institute follows the essential tenants for Manufacturing Innovation Institutes. Key design tenants of the network are captured within National Network for Manufacturing Innovation: A Preliminary Design, a report issued by the White House National Science and Technology Council on Jan. 16, 2013. These tenants are captured in the Advanced Manufacturing Partnership 2.0 (8). Fig. 4 illustrates institute overarching objective to develop manufacturing interactions of key components and demonstrating the manufacturing processes in commercial Defense applications. FHE exists in the intersection seam of two industries: the electronics industry and the high performance printing industry, both well-established US industrial and academic areas of strength. The intersection of these two industries offers a huge opportunity for continued growth and the FHE institute will increase US competitiveness in this emerging technology. For the electronics industry, commoditizing the die over new technologies and increasing the ease electronic packaging will provide increased economic growth into large product segments (e.g., medical, consumer, defense, etc.). For the domestic printing industry, harnessing high precision manufacturing technology for electronic devices will open up new markets to compete and thrive in a digital age. The FHE manufacturing ecosystem will enable novel commercial and Department of Defense products such as; wearable health monitoring for lifestyle and fitness, medical health monitoring to improve the way health care is managed, soft robotics for the elderly or wounded soldiers, sensor monitoring for structures, aircraft, or automotive, and light-weight rugged sensors for harsh environments.

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⁸ http://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/PCAST/amp20_report_final.pdf

Figure 1 – Typical current-voltage characteristic for an amorphous silicon thin film transistor with the TFT cross section.

Figure 2 – Flexible Digital x-ray imaging system and a flexible digital x-ray image array manufacturing at Arizona State University Flexible Display and Electronics Center. The x-ray package was developed by Xerox PARC.

Figure 3 – Illustration of a digital x-ray cross section and digital x-ray array.

Figure 4 – Illustration of basic construct the flexible hybrid electronic manufacturing institute; manufacturing focus and applications serviced.